

Diversity of Herptiles in Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

There are 10,450 reptile species recognized worldwide. There are 195 reptile species belong to 23 families. Pakistan is home to 13 reptile and 9 amphibian species. Several amphibian and reptile species have become extinct as a result of either direct or indirect anthropogenic effect. The research's aims were to estimate the variety of the studied region. During the study, total 16 herptiles species were documented, *Hemidactylus brookii* were noted with the highest relative (0.427419) and followed by *Calotes versicolor* (0.112903), *Bufo himalayanus* (0.104839), *Amphiesma stolatum* (0.072581), *Hemidactylus flaviviridis* (0.072581), *Ptyas mucosus mucosus* (0.040323), *Varanus bengalensis* (0.032258), *Scincella himalayana* (0.032258), *Laudakia agrorensis* (0.024194), *Eublepharis macularius* (0.016129), *Xenochrophis piscator piscator* (0.016129), *Gloydus himalayanus* (0.016129), *Bungarus caeruleus caeruleus* (0.008065), *Eryx johni* (0.008065), *Spalerosophis diadema diadema* (0.008065) and *Daboia russelii russelii* (0.008065). It is found that the district Bagh contains a diverse range of herptiles.

Keywords: Amphibian, Reptiles, Diversity, Bagh, Pakistan

Citation: Sultan, N., S. Adil, A. Nawaz. 2023. Diversity of Herptiles in Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. International Journal of Forest Sciences. 3: 12-17.

Received: January, 2023; **Accepted:** February, 2023

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan occurs a main geographic place (Sengor, 1985) and covers an area of 796,096 km² and is present in three zoogeographical zones (i.e., Palearctic, Oriental and Ethiopian). It stretches from longitude 60° to 75° E as well as latitude 24° to 37° N. Its southwest border is connected to the Arabian Sea, while its north end is located in the stable snow scenery of Pamir in the vast Himalayan region (Khan, 2006). The mountains and plateaus in the west, north, and northwest represent the major mountain. Its mountainous topography has had a significant impact on the climate, geology, hydrology, and physiography, as well as the distribution and composition of fauna and plants in the contemporary age (Khan, 2006). The other part in salt variety and base of Himalayas; it is one of earliest division of the subcontinents. It acts as earliest Tethys Sea (Powell, 1979; Khan, 2006).

Ten thousand four hundred and fifty species of reptiles are reported in the world (Utez, 2016); while 195 species present in Pakistan; belonging to 23 families (Khan, 2004, 2006). Pakistan has nine amphibian and thirteen reptile species (Khan et

al., 2004). Amphibians and reptiles are essential bio-indicators of climate change and may be present in a extensive variety of landscapes across the world, with the exception of a few isolated islands. Their abundance and variety are likewise connected to bird and mammalian diversity. Yet, the existence of herpetofauna, like that of many other species, is under constant threat owing to deforestation, habitat loss, urbanization, fragmentation, as well as pollution (Petrov, 2004). AmphibiaWeb (2018) currently noted that 7,850 amphibian species; out of total 714 are salamanders and newts, 6,929 are toads and frogs, and 20 are caecilians. Pakistan has high diversity of amphibian and reptiles species (Adil S *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Kamal and Faiz, 2022), herptiles are good bioindicators (Babar and Kanwal, 2021). Pakistan has 24 amphibian species (Khan, 2010). The study's major goal was to learn about the diversity of herptiles in Bagh, Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bagh is located 80 kilometers from Muzaffarabad. It is 160 kilometers from Islamabad, Pakistan's capital. The entire district Bagh is a hilly terrain, often sloping from northeast to south-west. The region is part of the lower Himalayas zone. Pir-Panjal is the district's primary range. The typical elevation is from 1500 to 2500 metres above sea level. Coniferous woods cover the majority of the highlands. Nonetheless, various more streams run through the region (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of the Study area.

The linear count technique was used to assess amphibian and reptile diversity using i) direct and ii) indirect counts. The “*direct count*” consists of physical presence and voices, whereas the “*indirect count method*” consists of meetings and question with peoples. The information was gathered between March 2016 and February 2017. The animals were observed using binoculars and a camera; Khan (2006) was used to accurately identify each one.

Data analysis

The “Shannon-wiener Diversity Index” is calculated with the help of MS excel by using this formula:

$$H' = -\sum(P_i \log P_i)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the research, total 16 herptiles species are documented (Table 1), *Hemidactylus Brookii* were noted with the highest relative abundance (0.427419) and followed by *Calotes versicolor*(0.112903), *Bufo himalayanus* (0.104839), *Amphiesma stolatum* (0.072581), *Hemidactylus flaviviridis* (0.072581), *Ptyas mucosus mucosus* (0.040323), *Varanus bengalensis* (0.032258), *Scincella himalayana* (0.032258), *Laudakia agrorensis* (0.024194), *Eublepharis macularius* (0.016129), *Xenochrophis piscator piscator* (0.016129), *Gloydus himalayanus* (0.016129), *Bungarus caeruleus caeruleus* (0.008065), *Eryx johni* (0.008065), *Spalerosophis diadema diadema* (0.008065) and *Daboia russelii russelii* (0.008065) (Table 2).

Table 1: Summary of the diversity of herpetofauna of Bagh.

Sr.	Scientific name	Species Authority	Common name	Family
1.	<i>Xenochrophis piscator</i>	Schneider, 1802	Chekered Keelback	Colubridae
2.	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	Daudin, 1802	Bengal monitor	Varanidae
3.	<i>Spalerosophis diadema</i>	Schelegel, 1837	Red spotted diadem snake	Colubridae
4.	<i>Scincella himalayana</i>	Gunther, 1864	Himalayan skink	Scinidae
5.	<i>Ptyas mucosus mucosus</i>	Linnaeus, 1758	Rope-snake	Colubridae
6.	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i>	Stoliczka, 1872	Agro agama	Agamidae
7.	<i>Hemidactylus flaviviridis</i>	Ruppell, 1835	Common house gecko	Gekkonidae
8.	<i>Hemidactylus Brookii</i>	Gray, 1845	Brooke's house gecko	Gekkonidae
9.	<i>Gloydus himalayanus</i>	Giinther, 1864	Himalayan pit viper	Viperidae
10.	<i>Eublepharis macularius</i>	Blyth, 1854	Fat tail gecko	Eublepharidae
11.	<i>Eryx johni</i>	Russell, 1801	Common sand boa	Boidae
12.	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i>	Shaw and Nodder, 1797	Russell's chain viper	Viperidae
13.	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	Daudin, 1802	Oriental Garden Lizard	Agamidae
14.	<i>Bungarus caeruleus</i>	Schneider, 1801	Common krait	Elapidae
15.	<i>Bufo himalayanus</i>	Gunther, 1864	Himalayan toad	Bufonidae
16.	<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i>	Linnaeus, 1758	Striped Keelback	Colubridae

Eublepharis macularius is recorded from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout the Pakistan. *Laudakia agrorensis* is documented from the Dhirkot. Khan (2005) Khan (2005) recorded from Neelum Valley AJK, Ooghey Valley, Mansehra and Abbottabad and Chitral, KPK. *Varanus bengalensis* is seen from Dhirkot. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout Pakistan. *Hemidactylus Brookii* is noted from the Dhirkot. Khan (2005) recorded from, Sindh, Punjab and AJK, Pakistan. *Daboia russelii* is observed from Dhirkot. Khan (2005) recorded from

Punjab and Sindh, Pakistan while Haider and Faiz (2020) from Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Checkered Keelback (*Xenochrophis piscator*) is recorded from study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout the Pakistan while Faiz and Farooq (2021) reported from Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Red spotted diadem snake (*Spalerosophis diadema*) is recorded from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout Pakistan. *Bungarus caeruleus* is observed from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout Pakistan.

Calotes versicolor is observed from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout Pakistan. *Gloydius himalayanus* is seen from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from AJK, Pakistan. *Hemidactylus flaviviridis* is recorded from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout plain areas (less than 1000 meter elevation) Pakistan. *Bufo himalayanus* is seen from Dhirkot. Khan (2005) also recorded from the Himalayan region of AJK at the elevation of 2000 to 3500 meter and also from NWFP. Himalayan skink (*Scincella himalayana*) is recorded from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from the Punjab, Waziristan and Chitral. Common Sand boa (*Eryx johni*) is recorded from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout Pakistan. Striped Keelback (*Amphiesma stolatum*) is recorded from the study area. Khan (2005) recorded from the Punjab and Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Ptyas mucosus* is seen from Dhirkot. Khan (2005) recorded from throughout Pakistan by Khan (2005).

During the study noted that these species were most common in the study area i.e. *Hemidactylus Brookii* and followed by *Hemidactylus Brookii*, *Calotes versicolor*, *Bufo himalayanus*, *Amphiesma stolatum*, *Hemidactylus flaviviridis*, *Ptyas mucosus mucosus*, *Varanus bengalensis*, *Scincella himalayana*, *Laudakia agrorensis* (Figure 2).

Table 2: Diversity of Herptiles of Bagh, Pakistan.

Sr.	Names	Pi	LogPi	PilogPi
5	<i>Xenochrophis piscator piscator</i>	0.016129	-1.79239	-0.02891
3	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	0.032258	-1.49136	-0.04811
12	<i>Spalerosophisdiadema diadema</i>	0.008065	-2.09342	-0.01688
9	<i>Scincella himalayana</i>	0.032258	-1.49136	-0.04811
13	<i>Ptyas mucosus mucosus</i>	0.040323	-1.39445	-0.05623
2	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i>	0.024194	-1.6163	-0.0391
4	<i>Hemidactylus brookii</i>	0.427419	-0.36915	-0.15778
8	<i>Gloydius himalayanus</i>	0.016129	-1.79239	-0.02891
1	<i>Eublepharis macularius</i>	0.016129	-1.79239	-0.02891
7	<i>Eryx johni</i>	0.008065	-2.09342	-0.01688
14	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i>	0.008065	-2.09342	-0.01688
11	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	0.112903	-0.94729	-0.10695
6	<i>Bungarus caeruleus caeruleus</i>	0.008065	-2.09342	-0.01688
10	<i>Bufo himalayanus</i>	0.104839	-0.97948	-0.10269
15	<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i>	0.072581	-1.13918	-0.08268
16	<i>Hemidactylus flaviviridis</i>	0.072581	-1.13918	-0.08268
Shannon-wiener Diversity Index				0.87859

CONCLUSION

During the study and research, it is found that district Bagh has diverse species of herptiles. Total 16 species of herptiles are documented and *Hemidactylus Brookii* is noted with the highest relative abundance.

Figure 2: Top abundant species in the study area.

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